

Regulation of Protein Synthesis in Animal Cells. A Study of the Mechanism of Co-eIF-2 Action

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THE first step in peptide chain initiation in mammalian cells is the formation of a ternary complex between eukaryotic peptide chain initiation factor 2 (eIF-2), Met-tRNA_i and GTP; Met-tRNA_i. eIF-2-GTP. There are indications that the ternary complex-forming activity of eIF-2 changes under different physiological conditions with accompanying changes in the protein synthesis activities in the cells. Recent reviews on the roles of eIF-2 in the regulation of eukaryotic protein synthesis initiation may be found¹⁻³.

Recent work done in our laboratory and elsewhere has indicated that the ternary complex formation by eIF-2 and its proper functioning during peptide chain initiation in animal cells is regulated by a complex mechanism involving eIF-2 ancillary protein factors, which we term Co-eIF-2 and RF, and also by eIF-2 kinases such as HRI (heme-regulated protein synthesis inhibitor) and dsI (double-stranded RNA-activated protein synthesis inhibitor)¹⁻³. Animal cells contain these eIF-2 kinases, in some cases, in inactive forms. Under certain physiological conditions, these eIF-2 kinases become activated and shut off protein synthesis. One of these eIF-2 kinases, HRI also called HCR (hemin-controlled repressor), is activated during heme deficiency in reticulocyte lysates and another eIF-2 kinase, dsI present in interferon-treated cells and also in reticulocyte, is activated in the presence of double-stranded RNAs. The activated eIF-2 kinases in both cases phosphorylate the smallest polypeptide component (α subunit) of eIF-2 and the eIF-2 α (P) thus formed is not recognised by eIF-2-ancillary protein factor(s) and is thus inactive in protein synthesis.

In this paper, our recent work on the characteristics of one of the eIF-2 ancillary protein factors, namely Co-eIF-2, and its role in the regulation of protein synthesis in animal cells is described. For our recent work on the other ancillary protein factor, may be seen^{1,4-6}.

Background :

Several years ago we reported the isolation of a low molecular weight polypeptide (Mr 25K) now termed Co-eIF-2A from rabbit reticulocyte ribosomal high salt wash⁷; Co-eIF-2A stimulated Met-tRNA_i binding to eIF-2 and also bound to the preformed ternary complex⁸ and stabilised the complex⁹. Antibodies prepared against homogeneous Co-eIF-2A (Mr 25K) strongly inhibited protein synthesis in

reticulocytes lysates and such inhibition was overcome by preincubation of the antibody specifically with homogeneous Co-eIF-2A, indicating that it was an essential component of protein synthesis in reticulocyte lysate¹⁰. Co-eIF-2A-like activity has been reported to be present in widely divergent eukaryotic organisms¹¹⁻¹³.

Previously we have also reported the isolation of a high molecular weight protein complex (Mr 450K) now termed Co-eIF-2 (Refs. 1, 19, 20) from reticulocyte ribosomal salt wash. In partial reactions, Co-eIF-2 showed the following effects on eIF-2 activity: (i) Co-eIF-2 stimulated the ternary complex formation by eIF-2 both in the presence and also in the absence of Mg²⁺. We termed this activity Co-eIF-2A. (ii) Co-eIF-2 stimulation of ternary complex formation by eIF-2 was most pronounced in the presence of Mg²⁺. Mg²⁺ inhibited the ternary complex formation by eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2 reversed this Mg²⁺ inhibition. We termed this activity Co-eIF-2C. This Co-eIF-2C activity was inhibited upon prior phosphorylation of eIF-2 α -subunit by HRI+ATP. (iii) The ternary complex preformed with Co-eIF-2 in the absence of Mg²⁺ dissociated extensively upon subsequent addition of Mg²⁺. The mechanism of this dissociation reaction and its physiological significance were not clearly understood. We termed this activity Co-eIF-2B (also termed TDF, ternary complex dissociation factor).

Co-eIF-2-like protein complex has also been isolated from reticulocyte ribosomal salt wash in Ochoa's laboratory (termed ESP²¹ and also in London's laboratory (termed SF²²). Workers from both these laboratories have reported that Co-eIF-2 reverses Mg²⁺ inhibition of the ternary complex formation by eIF-2 and this Mg²⁺ inhibition reversal activity is inhibited upon prior phosphorylation of eIF-2 by HRI and ATP^{21, 22}.

Recently, several workers have isolated Co-eIF-2-like high molecular weight protein complexes from reticulocyte cell supernatant²⁴⁻²⁶ and from ascites ribosomal salt wash^{20, 21}; these factors have been termed SP²³, GEF^{24, 25, 28, 30, 31}, RF²⁶, eIF-2B²⁷ and eRF²⁹. The following mechanism has been proposed for this factor activity, now widely termed as GEF (guanine nucleotide exchange factor). A significant part (approximately 50%) of the reticulocyte eIF-2 is isolated as eIF-2.GDP²⁵ and a recent report indicates that eIF-2 is released as eIF-2.GDP during peptide chain initiation³². In

the presence of Mg^{2+} , GDP remains tightly bound to eIF-2 and prevents ternary complex formation. GEF promotes GDP displacement from eIF-2.GDP and thus facilitates ternary complex formation; GEF does not promote GDP displacement from eIF-2 α (P).GDP (whose phosphorylation has been catalysed by HRI and ATP), but becomes physically bound to eIF-2 α (P).GDP and forms an inactive complex. GEF is present in reticulocyte lysate in limiting concentrations and protein synthesis in reticulocyte lysate ceases when only 30% of the eIF-2 becomes phosphorylated since this amount of eIF-2 α (P).GDP is sufficient to bind available GEF. Addition of exogenous GEF reverses protein synthesis inhibition in heme-deficient reticulocyte lysates as added GEF promotes GDP displacement from excess non-phosphorylated eIF-2.GDP and this facilitates ternary complex formation.

Purification of eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2 :

Scheme 1 shows the purification of eIF-2 and the eIF-2-ancillary protein factors which we term Co-eIF-2, Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ and RF from reticulocyte lysates. eIF-2, Co-eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ activities are purified from the 0.5 M KCl wash of reticulocyte ribosomes whereas the RF activity is purified from the cell supernatant. The bulk of Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ activity is not adsorbed onto a DEAE-cellulose column and so is separated from eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2. Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ activity has been further purified to homogeneity by heating, CM-Sephadex and hydroxylapatite chromatography^{7,8,9}.

eIF-2 activity co-purifies with Co-eIF-2 activity and is separated for the latter activity at the CM-Sephadex chromatographic step. The eIF-2 activity obtained after the CM-Sephadex chromatography has been further purified to homogeneity using phosphocellulose and hydroxylapatite chromatography^{8,9,10}. Co-eIF-2 activity has been further purified using hydroxylapatite and Heparin-Sephadex chromatography^{8,6}.

Characteristics of Co-eIF-2 :

Co-eIF-2 activity stimulates ternary complex formation by eIF-2 and also renders the complex stable. We have previously reported the isolation of a 25K polypeptide containing Co-eIF-2A activity⁷. We have now observed that reticulocyte high salt wash preparation contains, besides the 25K polypeptide, two other polypeptides (Mr 80K and 50K) which possess Co-eIF-2A activity^{8,9}. Moreover, we have obtained evidence that all three polypeptides containing Co-eIF-2A activities are components of Co-eIF-2 protein complex and that the lower molecular weight polypeptides (Mr 50K and 25K) are the protease degradation products of the 80K polypeptide.

All the Co-eIF-2A activities (termed Co-eIF-2A⁸⁵, Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ and Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰) co-purified during purification and were separated from each other during the last stage of purification using hydroxylapatite SDS column chromatography. Fig. 1 shows the SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis

Scheme 1. Purification scheme for eIF-2, and eIF-2-ancillary protein factors,

Fig. 1. SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of Co-eIF-2A⁵⁰, Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ and Co-eIF-2. The proteins were subjected to gel electrophoresis (10% polyacrylamide) in the presence of sodium dodecyl sulphate at pH 8.3. Lane 1, Co-eIF-2A⁵⁰; lanes 2-5, different Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ fractions; lane 5, Co-eIF-2. Data obtained from Ref. 31.

pattern of several hydroxylapatite column eluates and a partially purified Co-eIF-2 preparation. Lane 1 represents a middle fraction eluant at 150-170 mM potassium phosphate concentration, and lanes 2 through 5 represent four consecutive later fractions eluting between 180-250 mM potassium phosphate concentration. All the fractions showed strong Co-eIF-2A activity and the peak activity was observed with the preparation in lane 3. As shown here, lane 1 contained a major 50K polypeptide and two minor polypeptides in this molecular weight range (30K and 35K). Lanes 2 and 3 contain predominantly a 78K polypeptide, lane 4 contains a doublet (78K and 80K), and lane 5 contains predominantly an 80K polypeptide. As shown in lane 6, a partially purified Co-eIF-2 preparation also contains 80K and 50K polypeptides.

In another experiment we have demonstrated that homogeneous Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰, upon limited proteolysis with *Staphylococcus aureus* V8 protease, gave two polypeptide fragments (Mr 50K and 24K). The 80K polypeptide component(s) isolated from the SDS gel of Co-eIF-2 when treated similarly, also gave these two polypeptide fragments. These results show that Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ and the 80K polypeptide component in Co-eIF-2 are the same and that the lower molecular weight polypeptides are the protease degradation products of the 80K polypeptide. The results presented in Table 1 show the characteristic effects of the addition of Co-eIF-2A on Met-tRNA_f binding to eIF-2. These experiments were previously done using Co-eIF-2A²⁵. Similar results have also been obtained using Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰. As shown here,

addition of physiologically important compounds such as mRNAs and hemin, and also aurointricarboxylic acid, drastically reduced the Met-tRNA_f binding to eIF-2. Addition of Co-eIF-2A²⁵ stimulated the Met-tRNA_f binding to eIF-2 and this stimulated ternary complex formed in the presence of Co-eIF-2A²⁵ was almost fully resistant to globin mRNA, hemin and aurointricarboxylic acid. This observation suggests that the ternary complex does not exist in the free-form because it is too easily degraded in the presence of some normal cell components such as mRNA and hemin. The binding of Co-eIF-2A to ternary complex may stabilise it under physiological conditions.

TABLE 1—EFFECTS OF ADDITION OF Co-eIF-2A²⁵ ON Met-tRNA_f BINDING TO eIF-2

Additions	[³⁵ S]Met tRNA _f bound pmol	
	-Co-eIF-2A ²⁵	+Co-eIF-2A ²⁵
eIF-2	0.50	1.2
eIF-2 + Globin mRNA	0.10	1.1
eIF-2 + Hemin (50 μM)	0.06	0.9
eIF-2 + Aurintricarboxylic acid (30 μM)	0.10	1.0

Standard Millipore filtration assay conditions for Met-tRNA_f binding to eIF-2 were used. Data obtained from Ref. 7.

The requirement of Co-eIF-2A for protein synthesis in reticulocyte lysates was demonstrated using antibodies prepared against homogeneous Co-eIF-2A preparations^{10,33}. Addition of anti-Co-eIF-2A strongly inhibited protein synthesis in reticulocyte lysate and also eIF-2 + Co-eIF-2 promoted Met-tRNA_f binding to 40S ribosomes. Protein synthesis in reticulocyte lysate was almost completely reversed by preincubation of anti-Co-eIF-2A with homogeneous Co-eIF-2A and was partially reversed by similar preincubation of anti-Co-eIF-2A with Co-eIF-2. In another study, using a fluorescent polarisation technique, we provided evidence that the Co-eIF-2A²⁵ binds specifically to the ternary complex⁸.

Co-eIF-2C: As noted by others, Co-eIF-2 protein complex promotes GDP displacement from eIF-2.GDP and thus facilitates the ternary complex formation by eIF-2 (Refs. 24, 31). Homogeneous Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ does not possess this activity. The results presented in Table 2 describe the effects of the addition of Co-eIF-2 protein complex and Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ on ternary complex formation and GDP displacement in the presence and absence of Mg²⁺. We used preformed eIF-2.[³H]GDP in this experiment. As shown here (Table 2), in the absence of Mg²⁺, [³H]GDP was readily displaced from eIF-2.[³H]GDP, and both Co-eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ stimulated the ternary complex formation by eIF-2.[³H]GDP. In the presence of Mg²⁺, the [³H]GDP remained tightly bound to eIF-2 and ternary complex formation was significantly inhibited. Co-eIF-2 promoted displacement of [³H]GDP from eIF-2.[³H]GDP facilitated ternary complex formation while Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ was completely ineffective

TABLE 2—EFFECTS OF ADDITIONS OF Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ AND Co-eIF-2 ON TERNARY COMPLEX FORMATION AND GDP DISPLACEMENT IN THE PRESENCE AND ABSENCE OF Mg²⁺

Factors added	-Mg ²⁺		+Mg ²⁺	
	[³⁵ S]Met-tRNA _f bound pmol	[³ H]GDP retained pmol	[³⁵ S]Met-tRNA _f bound pmol	[³ H]GDP retained pmol
eIF-2.[³ H]GDP	1.6	0.5	0.6	2.6
eIF-2.[³ H]GDP + Co-eIF-2A ⁸⁰	3.5	0.4	1.2	2.7
eIF-2.[³ H]GDP + Co-eIF-2	4.4	0.3	3.3	0.4

Standard Millipore filtration assay conditions were used in the presence or absence of 1 mM Mg²⁺. Amounts of different factors used were : eIF-2.[³H]GDP, 1.2 μg; Co-eIF-2, 8 μg; Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰, 5 μg. Data obtained from Ref. 35.

in the GDP displacement. Some small stimulation of ternary complex formation by Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ might be due to the presence of eIF-2 molecules which do not contain bound GDP.

The above results suggest that Co-eIF-2 contains two component activities : Co-eIF-2C activity promotes GDP displacement from eIF-2.[³H]GDP and facilitates ternary complex formation by eIF-2, and the Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ component stimulates ternary complex formation and also stabilises the complex.

Mechanism of Co-eIF-2C-promoted GDP displacement from eIF-2.GDP :

Siekierka *et al.*³⁵ have proposed that a step in peptide chain initiation is the Co-eIF-2-promoted displacement of GDP by GTP and the formation of eIF-2.GTP ; eIF-2.GTP then binds Met-tRNA_f and forms the ternary complex. To test this hypothesis we prepared eIF-2.[³H]GTP by incubating eIF-2.[³H]GDP with NDK plus ATP and studied the characteristics of the eIF-2.[³H]GTP thus formed for ternary complex formation and nucleotide displacement.

As shown in Table 3, eIF-2.[³H]GTP, like eIF-2.[³H]GDP, was completely stable in the presence of Mg²⁺, and [³H]GTP remained tightly bound to eIF-2. eIF-2.[³H]GTP did not bind Met-tRNA_f. In the presence of a large excess (260 μM) of added

GTP, a small exchange of [³H]GTP with exogenous GTP and some ternary complex formation were observed. The significance of this GTP exchange is not apparent and is probably nonenzymatic. Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ alone did not promote the GTP displacement or ternary complex formation by eIF-2.[³H]GTP. Likewise, no loss of [³H]GTP from eIF-2.[³H]GTP was observed in the presence of Co-eIF-2 and Met-tRNA_f. In the presence of exogenously added GTP, Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ did not promote [³H]GTP displacement from eIF-2.[³H]GTP but promoted some (1.1 pmol) ternary complex formation. This complex formation might be by activation of GTP-free eIF-2 molecules. As shown in the last line, Co-eIF-2 promoted almost complete displacement of [³H]GTP from eIF-2.[³H]GTP in the presence of externally added GTP and facilitated ternary complex formation.

The results above show that GTP like GDP remains tightly bound to eIF-2 in the presence of Mg²⁺. Apparently, the tight association of the nucleotide with eIF-2 is not limited to GDP, and is presumably not due to the high affinity of eIF-2 specifically for GDP. This observation is consistent with our postulation that eIF-2 undergoes changes into an inactive conformation in the presence of Mg²⁺, and the eIF-2 bound to GDP remains locked in this conformation. Co-eIF-2 activates the eIF-2 molecules and in this active state the bound GDP from eIF-2.GDP complex is freely displaced and ternary complex is formed.

Roles of Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ and Co-eIF-2 in Met-tRNA_f.40S initiation complex formation :

We have previously reported that eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2 promoted efficient Met-tRNA_f.40S.AUG complex formation^{1,38}. Using antibodies prepared against Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ we have previously provided evidence that the Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ component is required for Co-eIF-2-promoted Met-tRNA_f.40S complex formation³⁸. The results presented in Table 4 demonstrate that both the Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ component and also another component activity, possibly Co-eIF-2C, are required for eIF-2+Co-eIF-2-promoted Met-tRNA_f.40S complex formation.

We used preformed eIF-2.[³H]GDP in these experiments. As noted earlier, [³H]GDP was freely displaced from eIF-2.[³H]GDP in the absence of

TABLE 3—EFFECTS OF ADDITION OF DIFFERENT FACTORS ON TERNARY COMPLEX FORMATION AND [³H]GTP DISPLACEMENT FROM eIF-2.[³H]GTP

Additions	[³ H]GTP retained pmol	[³⁵ S]Met-tRNA _f bound pmol
None	2.1	—
Met-tRNA _f	1.9	0.1
Met-tRNA _f +GTP	1.4	0.4
Met-tRNA _f +Co-eIF-2A ⁸⁰	2.1	0.1
Met-tRNA _f +Co-eIF-2	2.0	0.6
Met-tRNA _f +GTP+Co-eIF-2A ⁸⁰	2.1	1.1
Met-tRNA _f +GTP+Co-eIF-2	0.1	2.7

A two-stage assay method was used. In stage I, eIF-2.[³H]GTP was prepared by incubating eIF-2.[³H]GDP with NDK and ATP. The reaction mixtures were then mixed with Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰, Co-eIF-2, GTP and Met-tRNA_f as indicated and were incubated under standard Millipore filtration assay conditions for ternary complex formation. Data obtained from Ref. 35.

TABLE 4—FACTOR REQUIREMENTS OF Met-tRNA_f. eIF-2-GTP AND Met-tRNA_f.40S.AUG COMPLEX FORMATION

Additions	1st Stage		2nd Stage
	[³ H]GDP retained pmol	[³⁵ S]Met-tRNA _f bound to eIF-2 pmol	[³⁵ S]Met-tRNA _f transferred to 40S ribosomes pmol
eIF-2.[³ H]GDP	0.4	1.6	0.4
eIF-2.[³ H]GDP + Co-eIF-2A ⁸⁰	0.5	3.1	0.4
eIF-2.[³ H]GDP + Co-eIF-2	0.4	2.4	0.9
eIF-2.[³ H]GDP + Co-eIF-2 + Co-eIF-2A ⁸⁰	0.5	3.2	1.4

A two-stage assay method was used. In stage I, ternary complex was formed by incubating eIF-2.[³H]GDP, GTP, salt mixture, [³⁵S]Met-tRNA_f and where indicated Co-eIF-2, Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ at 37° for 5 min. In stage II, 2 mM magnesium acetate, AUG and 40S ribosomes were added and the reaction mixtures were further incubated at 37° for 5 min. [³⁵S]Met-tRNA_f bound to 40S ribosomes was then assayed using the standard procedure. Data obtained from Ref. 35.

Mg²⁺, and both Co-eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ stimulated the ternary complex formation by eIF-2.[³H]GDP with accompanying [³H]GDP displacement. However, this stimulated ternary complex which was formed in the presence of Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ was completely inactive Met-tRNA_f.40S initiation complex formation. On the other hand, the addition of limiting accounts of Co-eIF-2 showed half-maximal stimulation of ternary complex formation in the absence of Mg²⁺ and gave half-maximal stimulation of Met-tRNA_f binding to 40S ribosomes. As shown here, when the limiting amount of Co-eIF-2 was added in addition to excess Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰, no further stimulation of the ternary complex formation was observed. However, the Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ stimulated ternary complex was now active in the Met-tRNA_f.40S initiation complex formation, whereas it had been inactive in the absence of Co-eIF-2.

The above results indicate that both Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰ and another component activity in Co-eIF-2 are required for Met-tRNA_f.40S initiation complex formation. The latter activity is required to render the Co-eIF-2A⁸⁰-stimulated ternary complex competent in Met-tRNA_f.40S complex formation. The relationship of Co-eIF-2C with this Co-eIF-2 component activity which is necessary for Met-tRNA_f.40S initiation complex formation is not clear. We have suggested that this component activity is necessary for the activation of eIF-2 and for the formation of functional ternary complexes. It is possible that the Co-eIF-2C component in Co-eIF-2 is also involved in this activation and, as we have suggested earlier, in this activated state, guanine nucleotides (GDP or GTP) bound to eIF-2 are readily displaced by GTP during ternary complex formation.

A proposed mechanism of Co-eIF-2 action :

Based on the results presented above and previously, we proposed a mechanism of functional

ternary complex formation by eIF-2 (Scheme 2). A two-step activation of eIF-2 has been envisioned. eIF-2 is isolated partly as free eIF-2 (GDP-free) and partly as eIF-2.GDP. One of the activation steps involves the Co-eIF-2A component in Co-eIF-2. This activation results in stimulated Met-tRNA_f binding to GDP-free eIF-2 and this effect is most apparent with aged eIF-2 preparations and also in the absence of Mg²⁺ as GDP in eIF-2.GDP is readily displaced by GTP during ternary complex formation in the absence of Mg²⁺. The stimulated ternary complex formed in the presence of Co-eIF-2A alone is not functional in Met-tRNA_f.40S initiation complex formation. Such competency is acquired by a second activation by the Co-eIF-2C component in Co-eIF-2. This activation step is involved in maintaining an active conformation of eIF-2 and in this conformation the bound guanine nucleotides (GDP or GTP) are readily displaced by GTP during functional ternary complex formation. Both Co-eIF-2A and also Co-eIF-2 protein complexes render the ternary complex stable to physiological mRNAs and aurointricarboxylic acid. Our previous studies indicated physical binding of Co-eIF-2A⁸⁵ to the preformed ternary complex⁸ and formation of stable quaternary complexes. eIF-2 kinases such as HRI phosphorylates eIF-2.GDP and blocks the Co-eIF-2C-promoted activation step.

Requirements of eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2 for Met-tRNA_f.40S complex formation with AUG codon and physiological mRNAs :

Despite numerous reports from many workers, the precise mechanism and factor requirements for Met-tRNA_f.40S initiation complex formation are not clearly understood. Several groups have reported the requirements of multiple protein factors such as eIF-1, eIF-2, eIF-3, eIF-4A, eIF-4B, eIF-4C and CBP (cap binding protein) for the formation of Met-tRNA_f.40S preinitiation complexes with physiological mRNAs^{2,9,40}.

Several years ago we reported^{8,88} that eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2 protein complex promote AUG-codon dependent Met-tRNA_f binding to 40S ribosomes. The requirements for eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2-like protein complexes for AUG-codon dependent Met-tRNA_f.40S complex formation have subsequently been reported by London's laboratory⁴¹ and Ochoa's laboratory⁴². Also, there is agreement that such Met-tRNA_f.40S.AUG complex formation is strongly inhibited by a physiological protein synthesis inhibitor, HRI, thus mimicking a physiological condition.

However, our previous attempts to use the same factor combination for a physiological mRNA-dependent Met-tRNA_f.40S initiation complex formation have not been successful. Recently, we have observed that replacement of GTP by a nonhydrolysable GTP analog, GMP-PNP, in the standard reaction mixture promoted significant Met-tRNA_f.40S preinitiation complex formation dependent on a physiological mRNA, such as globin mRNA^{43,44}.

Scheme 2. A proposed mechanism for formation of functional initiation complex by eIF-2. A two-step activation of eIF-2 molecules has been proposed. eIF-2 molecules in different activated forms are indicated as follows: eIF-2^o, inactive form; eIF-2^{*}, partially activated form; eIF-2^{**}, fully activated form. Data obtained from Ref. 85.

Significant stimulation of Met-tRNA_f binding to 40S ribosomes was also observed when GTP was used in the presence of nucleoside 5'-diphosphate kinase (NDK) and ATP. ATP alone in the absence of NDK had no effect.

Figs. 2 and 3 describe the requirements for Met-tRNA_f 40S complex formation with AUG-codon and globin mRNA. [³⁵S]Met-tRNA_f bound to 40S ribosomes was analysed by density gradient centrifugation followed by the Millipore filtration of the gradient fractions and radioactivity measurement. As reported previously, eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2 efficiently stimulated Met-tRNA_f binding to 40S ribosomes in the presence of AUG codon. The same factor combination, however, failed to promote significant Met-tRNA_f binding to 40S ribosomes in the presence of globin mRNA (Fig. 2A). The addition of NDK and ATP did not have any significant effect on AUG-dependent Met-tRNA_f binding to 40S ribosomes, but caused a significant increase in globin mRNA-dependent Met-tRNA_f binding (Fig. 2B). When GTP was replaced by GMP-PNP in the standard reaction mixture both AUG codon and globin mRNA stimulated signi-

ficantly Met-tRNA_f binding to 40S ribosomes (Fig. 2C). Also, the efficiencies of Met-tRNA_f binding to 40S ribosomes were significantly enhanced (compare panel A and B with C). Fig. 3 shows the factor requirements for globin mRNA-dependent Met-tRNA_f binding to 40S ribosomes in the presence of GMP-PNP. The requirements of both eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2 for such complex formations are clearly evident.

Using [¹⁴C] radioactively-labeled eIF-2, we have also observed significant binding of [¹⁴C]eIF-2 to 40S ribosomes dependent on Co-eIF-2 and mRNA when GMP-PNP was used in place of GTP in the standard reaction mixture⁴¹. Again, significant binding of [¹⁴C]eIF-2 to 40S ribosomes was observed when GTP was used with NDK + ATP.

Based on our observations on the requirements of GMP-PNP or GTP + NDK + ATP for both Met-tRNA_f 40S preinitiation complex formation with physiological mRNAs and [¹⁴C]eIF-2 binding to 40S ribosomes, we have postulated that the ternary complex (Met-tRNA_f eIF-2.GTP) first binds to 40S ribosomes and then eIF-2 is released as eIF-2.GDP.

Fig. 2. Requirements for Met-tRNA₁ 40S initiation complex formation with AUG-codon and globin mRNA. Standard sucrose density gradient centrifugation assay methods were used. Data obtained from Ref. 42.

Fig. 3. Factor requirements for Met-tRNA₁ 40S globin mRNA complex formation using GMP-PNP. The assay conditions were the same as in Figure 2. Where indicated eIF-2, Co-eIF-2 and globin mRNA were omitted from the complete reaction mixture. Data obtained from Ref. 42.

In the presence of AUG codon, a substantial part of Met-tRNA₁ remains stably bound to 40S ribosomes after the release of eIF-2. Similar Met-tRNA₁ 40S complexes formed with physiological mRNAs are possibly unstable and dissociate under *in vitro* conditions. In the presence of GTP + NDK + ATP or GMP-PNP (in place of GTP), the intact ternary complex remains stably bound to 40S ribosomes and confers added stability to the Met-tRNA₁ 40S initiation complexes formed with physiological mRNAs. This postulated mechanism is shown using AUG codon and mRNA (physiological) as follows :

This mechanism is consistent with a previous report that GTP hydrolysis occurs when methionyl tRNA₁ is bound to 40S ribosomes and without the interaction of the 60S ribosomal subunit⁴⁵.

Conclusions :

In this paper, the results of our recent studies using a high molecular weight reticulocyte protein complex which we term Co-eIF-2 have been

reviewed. Co-eIF-2 protein complex has been extensively purified starting from 0.5 M KCl wash of reticulocyte ribosomes^{9,10}. Upon polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis, purified Co-eIF-2 preparation shows a single protein band under non-denaturing conditions. Also, Co-eIF-2 activity sediments as a fairly symmetrical peak upon glycerol density gradient centrifugation, indicating that this Co-eIF-2 preparation is fairly homogeneous. Upon SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis, the Co-eIF-2 protein complex shows six polypeptide bands^{9,10}. We have provided evidence that some of the polypeptide bands, such as Co-eIF-2A²⁵ and Co-eIF-2A₅₀ present in a partially purified Co-eIF-2 preparation^{9,11} are the result of protease degradation of higher molecular weight polypeptide components.

This Co-eIF-2 protein complex contains multiple component activities. We have provided evidence that at least two component activities, namely Co-eIF-2A and Co-eIF-2C, are required for the Met-tRNA_f 40S initiation complex formation and that the Co-eIF-2A activity is also required for over all protein synthesis in reticulocyte lysates. Co-eIF-2C activity promotes GDP displacement from eIF-2.GDP and this facilitates ternary complex formation by eIF-2. The result of our experiments suggest that Co-eIF-2C activity is involved in the activation of eIF-2 molecules and in this activated state, GDP bound to eIF-2 is readily displaced by GTP during ternary complex formation. This proposed mechanism of activation is consistent with our observation that a component in Co-eIF-2 is necessary to render the preformed ternary complex competent in Met-tRNA_f 40S initiation complex formation.

Our recent report regarding the requirements of eIF-2 and Co-eIF-2 for Met-tRNA_f 40S initiation complex formation with a physiological mRNA raises several questions related to the basic mechanism and factor requirements for Met-tRNA_f 40S.mRNA complex formation. According to the widely accepted mechanism of eukaryotic peptide chain initiation proposed by Staehelin, Anderson, Hershey and coworkers, eight ribosomal protein factors such as eIF-1, eIF-2, eIF-3, eIF-4A, eIF-4B, eIF-4C, CBP (cap binding protein) and eIF-5 are required for peptide chain initiation in reticulocyte lysate^{9,10,40}. The ternary complex, Met-tRNA_f.eIF-2.GTP binds to 40S ribosomes in the absence of any factor or mRNA. The factors, eIF-1 and eIF-3 stabilise Met-tRNA_f bound to 40S ribosomes. The factors eIF-3, eIF-4A, eIF-4B, eIF-4C together with ATP are required to direct mRNA binding to Met-tRNA_f.eIF-2.GTP.40S complex. The CBP is also required for binding of capped mRNAs to 40S ribosomes. Met-tRNA_f.eIF-2.GTP.40S.mRNA complex binds to 60S ribosomes in the presence of eIF-5 and forms Met-tRNA_f.80S.mRNA. This joining step is accompanied with the hydrolysis of GTP and release of eIF-2 as eIF-2.GDP. Our observations regarding the require-

ments of Met-tRNA_f.40S.mRNA complex formation are indicated below. (i) Presence of mRNA is required for optimum Met-tRNA_f binding to 40S ribosomes. (ii) Only two factors eIF-2+Co-eIF-2 are required for Met-tRNA_f.40S complex formation with a physiological mRNA, namely globin mRNA. Co-eIF-2 protein complex contains multiple polypeptide components. The possibility remains open that some of the factor activities reported by Staehelin, Anderson and Hershey are present in this high molecular weight protein complex. (iii) There is no indication that ATP is required for Met-tRNA_f.40S complex formation with globin mRNA. (iv) GTP hydrolysis occurs after the ternary complex is bound to 40S ribosomes and the eIF-2 is released as eIF-2.GDP.

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